

DEVELOPMENT OF AUTOMATIC REAL TIME WATER LEVEL MEASURING SYSTEM

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Abstract

The development of an automatic water level monitoring system is essential for efficient water management in various applications such as agriculture, industrial processes, and water reservoirs. This system leverages modern sensor technology, microcontrollers, and Internet of Things (IoT) integration to provide real-time water level data. An ultrasonic sensor is employed to measure water levels by transmitting sound waves and detecting their reflections, while a DS3231 Real-Time Clock (RTC) ensures accurate timestamping of data. The ESP32 microcontroller, with its built-in Wi-Fi capability, facilitates data transmission to cloud platforms for remote monitoring. A data logger, equipped with an SD card module, stores historical data for later analysis, ensuring reliable performance even during communication disruptions. The system is measured water level with highest R² value of 0.9994 which shows the sensor measure accurate values. The system is designed to be energy-efficient and can operate autonomously, powered by battery or external power sources. This water level monitoring solution enhances automation, reduces manual labour, and improves water resource management, making it highly beneficial for smart water management systems.

Keywords: Water level monitoring, IoT integration, Ultrasonic sensor, Real-time data, ESP32 microcontroller, Smart water management etc

Introduction

Water is one of the most essential things of all living beings. It plays an essential role in the agricultural, transport, fishing and industrial sectors, as well as for domestic and recreational applications. These reasons, coupled with high demand and limited supply, as well as rapid population growth, make it necessary to reserve water in dams, above ground and underground reservoirs for future use. [1]. Liquid levels are measured in a variety of agricultural applications, fuel tanks, water reservoirs, irrigation canals, and evaporation pans, [6]. In some water fields such flood warning systems, irrigation systems, power plants and research, water level data is important. In most cases, water level measurement was done manually, but it was inefficient due to problems such as difficulty in reaching the measurement point, human error, etc. Some automatic water level measurement systems have been designed with mechanical sensors such as resistors.[2], capacitive sensors [10] or magnetic [16], but these sensors must be directly connected to water and their life will be short due to corrosion. In addition, resistive and magnetic sensors can only measure the water level in certain areas. A The capacitive sensor can measure the water

level anywhere, but the composition of the water affects the measurement result. On the other hand, this system uses an ultrasonic sensor that can measure the water level without touching the water, which will extend the service life. A microcontroller is used in this system as a data processor and controller for other electronic components. This system writes the measurement result on the SD card as CSV. This means that the file does not need to go directly to the measurement point. The main objective of this research is to design and build a system that can automatically measure the water level on a microcontroller and can record the measurement result for a long time on the SD card and then analyse the results.

Experimental Details

The main device of the water level monitoring system is the ESP32, which is used to store and process the data collected by the various sensors mentioned above. The data collected by the ultrasonic sensor is stored on an SD card and sent and displayed in the Excel. In addition, the entire system can be powered by a power bank. The detailed block diagram of the IoT-based infiltration monitoring system is shown in Fig. 1.

Hardware And Software System

HC-SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor

The ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04 is based on the technology of transmission and reception of ultrasonic sound like bat. The sensor emits a sound pulse at a frequency of 40 kHz and hears the sound. Compared to other sensors, the HC-SR04 does not focus on the sun and black objects. [3,9] It measures the distance to an object by emitting an ultrasonic wave and detecting the time it takes for the wave to return after reflecting off the object.

The ultrasonic sensor is designed to function in coordination with commands from a microcontroller. The HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor features four pins: Vcc, ground, echo, and trigger. The echo and trigger

pins are linked to the microcontroller's I/O pins. The microcontroller manages the water level measurement process based on the sensor's timing diagram, ensuring proper synchronization between the sensor and the system.

It works with the trigger and echo method. The transmitter module triggers and sends the signal to the water, the water returns an echo signal that is read by the echo, that is, the receiver module. The wave is transmitted for 200 microseconds, and with a speed of around 340 meters per second (the speed of sound in air), The ultrasonic sensor calculates the distance of the signal and returns the water level. The travel time value and the velocity value allow the sensor to calculate the water level [15].

Fig. 2 Working of Ultrasonic sensor

ESP32 Devkit V1

The ESP32 Devkit V1, is used in this project as a development board designed by DOIT to work with the ESP-WROOM-32 module The ESP32 module is made by Espressif Systems, in particular, a low-cost and low-power microcontroller package, with integrated Wi-Fi and dual-mode Bluetooth connection all on single board.[5] It offers 30 digital input/output pins, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button, providing all the necessary

components to support the microcontroller.

The ESP32 module is a Wi-Fi / Bluetooth solution that not only provides wireless connectivity, but also an internal processor and connectors to connect various external devices with input and output pins on the microcontroller. There are two processor cores that can independently control operating frequencies between 80 MHz and 240 MHz, making them more efficient than other low-cost microcontrollers. [2]

Fig. 3 ESP32 Devkit V1 module

SD card module

A data logger is an electronic device designed to record data over time or at specific locations, either using built-in sensors or external ones. Typically compact, battery-powered, and portable, data loggers are equipped with a microprocessor, internal memory for data storage, and sensors for data acquisition. One of their key advantages is the ability

to automatically collect real-time data continuously, often over 24-hour periods. Once activated, they function autonomously, recording data without needing constant supervision. In this project, an SD card module is integrated with the IoT-based instrument to store recorded data or historical data

Fig.4 SD card module

RTC module

RTC modules are simple timekeeping systems that use a battery to continue running even when external power is lost. They ensure that time and date information is always up to date. The DS3231, a cost-effective and highly accurate real-time clock, can record hours, minutes, seconds, and date information such as days, months, and years, with automatic adjustments for leap years and months with fewer than 31 days. The module

operates on either 3.3V or 5V, making it compatible with a wide range of development platforms and microcontrollers. It features a built-in Temperature Compensated Crystal Oscillator (TCXO) and a crystal to maintain precise timekeeping. Additionally, it includes a battery input to preserve accurate time even when the device's main power supply is interrupted.

Fig.5 RTC module

2.1.5 Arduino IDE The Arduino IDE is an editor used to write programs, compile and upload them to the Arduino board. The Arduino development environment consists of a text editor for writing code, a message area, a text keyboard, a toolbar with buttons for common functions, and a set of menus. The Arduino Software IDE makes it easy to write code and upload it to the board offline. We recommend it for

users with poor or no internet connection. This software can be used with any controller board. There are currently two versions of the Arduino IDE, one is the IDE 1. Arduino IDE uses a variant of the C++ programming language. The code is written in C++ with an addition of special methods and functions.[6]

2.3 SCHEMATIC CIRCUIT

Fig.5 Circuit diagram of proposed system

Working principle of the water level measurement system in the tank

The system uses an ultrasonic sensor to measure the water level by sending a sound wave towards the bottom of the tank. The wave is reflected from the bottom and returns to the sensor. The time required for this round trip is recorded. The water level is therefore calculated using the formula.

$$\text{Distance Measured} = \frac{(\text{Elapsed Time} \times \text{Speed of Sound})}{2}$$

where:

Elapsed Time is the duration for the sound wave to travel to the bottom and back. Speed of Sound is generally 340 m/s in air. The division by 2 accounts for the distance travelled by the wave in both directions. This calculation provides the current distance to the water level from the sensor.

Fig.6 Flow chart of working of proposed system

The real-time automatic water level measurement system operates by first initializing the HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor and ESP32 microcontroller. Once the system is ready, it captures water level data using the ultrasonic sensor, which is then processed by the ESP32. The data, along with a timestamp from the RTC module, is saved locally on an SD card for backup. The system then transmits the data wirelessly to a remote user or server via the ESP32's Wi-Fi module, allowing for real-time monitoring. Finally, the data is displayed in Excel for easy visualization and analysis. This approach provides a reliable and automated solution for continuous water level monitoring.

Results and Discussion

The proposed system was tested for a small water tank as shown in Fig. 1 and the water level was measured using a scale and a water level sensor at time intervals and at different depths as shown in table 1. The data measured by the sensor measurement is compared with the actual data and finds the difference, the correction factor and the error percentage for the proposed system.

Fig. 7 Actual proposed measurement system

Table 1. Measurement of Actual and sensor water level

Actual	Sensor	Difference	Correction factor	Calibrated value	Error %
1	0.79	0.21	1.27	0.82	0.82
2.5	2.27	0.23	1.1	2.36	2.36
4	3.7	0.3	1.08	3.85	3.85
5.5	5.59	-0.09	0.98	5.81	5.81
7	6.62	0.38	1.06	6.88	6.88
8.5	8.13	0.37	1.05	8.46	8.46
10	9.93	0.07	1.01	10.33	10.33
11.5	11.03	0.47	1.04	11.47	11.47
13	12.42	0.58	1.05	12.92	12.92
14.5	14.34	0.16	1.01	14.91	14.91
16	15.85	0.15	1.01	16.48	16.48
17.5	17.35	0.15	1.01	18.04	18.04
18	17.87	0.13	1.01	18.58	18.58
18.5	18.23	0.27	1.01	18.96	18.96
19	18.76	0.24	1.01	19.51	19.51
19.5	19.21	0.29	1.02	19.98	19.98
20	19.72	0.28	1.01	20.51	20.51
Average		0.2465	1.0429		1.2608

Fig. 9 Regression analysis of the calibration and validation of actual and sensor water level

The sensor shows an error of 21% at a true value of 1, but the accuracy improves with increasing values, with errors falling below 0.1% at higher readings. A correction factor, ranging from 1.04 to 1.27, is applied to improve the accuracy of the sensor. After calibration, the error in the lowest value drops to 0.82%, which shows the effectiveness

of this regulation. After calibration, the fit is also improved, with the calibration plot having a slope of nearly 1 and a ($R^2 = 0.9896$), indicating accurate sensor performance after correction. Validation plot showing a strong linear relationship between actual and sensor values ($R^2 = 0.9894$).

The sensor initially showed significant errors at low readings, but accuracy improved with higher values. After applying a correction factor, the error at the lowest reading was greatly reduced, significantly enhancing the sensor's accuracy. Calibration resulted in a near-perfect fit, indicating a strong linear relationship between the corrected sensor and actual values. Validation further confirmed that the calibration successfully corrected inaccuracies, ensuring reliable sensor performance across the measurement range.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this research demonstrates the successful development and validation of an automatic real-time water level measurement system. Integrating sensor technologies with calibration techniques, the system achieves high accuracy over a wide range of water levels, with particularly noticeable improvements after the application of correction factors. Initial measurement errors, especially at lower levels, were effectively minimized, confirming the reliability of the system for continuous monitoring in dynamic environments.

Data analysis and validation for regression models showed a strong correlation between actual values and sensors, reinforcing the accuracy of the system after calibration. This real-time water level measurement system provides a convenient, efficient and scalable solution for various applications such as irrigation management, flood monitoring and reservoir control, where accurate and timely data is essential for decision making. Future improvements can focus on further reducing the initial measurement error and expanding the applicability of the system to more diverse environmental conditions.

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